

Model of Community Management for Sustainable Utilization

Luedech Girdwichai, Witthaya Mekhum

I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract—This research intended to develop the model of community management for sustainable utilization by investigating on 2 groups of population, the family heads and the community management team. The population of the former group consisted of family heads from 511 families in 12 areas to complete the questionnaires which were returned at 479 sets. The latter group consisted of the community management team of 12 areas with 1 representative from each area to give the interview. The questionnaires for the family heads consisted of 2 main parts; general information such as occupations, etc. in the form of checklist. The second part dealt with the data on self reliance community development based on 4P Framework, i.e., People (human resource) development, Place (area) development, Product (economic and income source) development, and Plan (community plan) development in the form of rating scales. Data in the 1st part were calculated to find frequency and percentage while those in the 2nd part were analyzed to find arithmetic mean and SD. Data from the 2nd group of population or the community management team were derived from focus group to find factors influencing successful management together with the in depth interview which were analyzed by descriptive statistics. The results showed that 479 family heads reported that the aspect on the implementation of community plan to self reliance community activities based on Sufficient Economy Philosophy and the 4P was at the average of 3.28 or moderate level. When considering in details, it was found that the 1st aspect was on the area development with the mean of 3.71 or high level followed by human resource development with the mean of 3.44 or moderate level, then, economic and source of income development with the mean of 3.09 or moderate level. The last aspect was community plan development with the mean of 2.89. The results from the small group discussion revealed some factors and guidelines for successful community management as follows: 1) on the People (human resource) development aspect, there was a project to support and develop community leaders. 2) On the aspect of Place (area) development, there was a development on conservative tourism areas. 3) On the aspect of Product (economic and source of income) development, the community leaders promoted the setting of occupational group, saving group, and product processing group. 4) On the aspect of Plan (community plan) development, there was a prioritization through public hearing.

Keywords—Model of community management, sustainable utilization.

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THE mission of the Ministry of Interior is to “eliminate hardship, create prosperity” for people of the country by setting the integration management policy with people center. This can be implemented by preparing the readiness of community to increase potential driving force and maintain sustainable self reliance using the integration management policy for conducting community process management together with the local wisdom. The Department of Community Development is responsible for implementing the community management strategic policy based on sustainable development [1]. As can be seen in the policy of the National Development Plan issue 10 (2008-2012) that the country should be ready for the change of globalization. Sufficient Economy Philosophy is a good guideline to develop and manage the country by being rationale, sufficient, immunized, and knowledgeable as an indicator for the evaluation of sustainable utilization of the community [2]. There has been an emerge of community agenda based on 4P Framework to develop the country and the community for sustainable growth of quality economic under the rapid unpredictable and complicated internal and external change. The National Development Plan issue 11 defined the target and the development strategy by encouraging immunity to prevent from risk factors and strengthen the country foundation together with human and social development of the country [3]. This includes the chance to fairly access resources and to achieve the benefit of economic development in addition with creating knowledge base and creativity based on environmental friendly production and consumption leading to sustainable development of the country.

With the problems mentioned above, the researcher applied the idea and policy of the Department of Community Development, Ministry of Interior to develop community plan. This involved with the 3 main pillars including self reliance, cooperation plan of the community, and policy supporting plan to create the prototype of Sufficient Economy community based on the people’s needs. This supports the policy of the Department of Community Development and the policy of the Ministry of Interior as well as the policy of Office of the Royal projects Board (ORDPB) working on the Sufficient Economy Philosophy to apply in the community.

II. OBJECTIVES

This research intended to develop the model of community management for sustainable utilization.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Scope of the Area

The researcher divided the study areas according to the development areas of the Department of Community Development, Ministry of Interior in 12 areas as follows:

TABLE I
RESEARCH AREAS FOR DATA COLLECTION

Area	Area
Area 1 Nakornnayok	Area 7 Samudsongkram
Area 2 Sakaew	Area 8 Chumporn
Area 3 Nakornpanom	Area 9 Trang
Area 4 Konkaen	Area 10 Nonthaburi
Area 5 Lampang	Area 11 Nakornratchasima
Area 6 Pitsanuloke	Area 12 Nakornsawan

B. Scope of the Content

The criteria to develop the research framework were from the 4P Framework of the Department of Community Development on the policy of driving the community agenda by the Ministry of Interior, 2554 BE which are:

- People (human resource) development
- Place (area) development
- Product (economic and income source) development
- Plan (community plan) development

C. Population and Sampling Group

Two groups of population were the family heads and the community management team. The population of the former group consisted of family heads from 511 families in 12 areas to complete the questionnaires which were returned at 479 sets. The latter group consisted of the community management team of 12 areas with 1 representative from each area to give the interview (see Table II).

TABLE II
POPULATION AND RESEARCH SAMPLING GROUP

Area	Province	Population	Sampling group
1	Nakornnayok	26	23
2	Sakaew	81	80
3	Nakornpanom	49	47
4	Konkaen	58	55
5	Lampang	47	43
6	Pitsanuloke	52	45
7	Samudsongkram	26	24
8	Chumporn	35	33
9	Trang	26	23
10	Nonthaburi	27	25
11	Nakornratchasima	54	56
12	Nakornsawan	30	25
Total	12	511	479

D. Research Tools

To collect data in this study, the research tools included questionnaires and focus group.

1. Questionnaires for family heads consisted of 2 main parts.

Part 1: General information of the subjects such as occupations and other personal details in the form of checklist.

The data in this part were analyzed to find frequency and percentage through computer program.

Part 2: This dealt with the data on self reliance community development based on 4P Framework, i.e., People (human resource) development, Place (area) development, Product (economic and income source) development, and Plan (community plan) development in the form of rating scales. The data in this part were analyzed to find arithmetic mean and SD from the 5 rating scales.

2. Focus group of the community management team to give the information of factors influencing successful management. The small group meeting was recorded for the content analysis. The data were categorized and organized to find the relationship of the framework. This included the synthesis of variables affecting the sustainable development of the community. The results are presented in descriptive and report forms.

IV. RESULTS

A. Results of the Questionnaires

The findings from the questionnaires revealed that most population or 94.6% had their own accommodations. Most of their occupations were agriculture or 76.6%. Most of them were heads of the families at 69.1%. They reported their education level lower than Primary education at 66.2%. On the participation of the process of community management, most of them or 64.5% never joined the process before. More than half of the informants or 64.5% were over 50 years old. About 58.9% got additional jobs and 58% had sufficient income. There were 55.9% male and 51.1% female.

The principles of community reliance were from 4P Framework, i.e., People (human resource) development, Place (area) development, Product (economic and income source) development, and Plan (community plan) development. In general, the average of 4 aspects was 3.28 or moderate level. When considering in details, it was found that the 1st aspect was on the area development with the mean of 3.71 or high level followed by human resource development with the mean of 3.44 or moderate level, then, economic and source of income development with the mean of 3.09 or moderate level. The last aspect was community plan development with the mean of 2.89 as can be seen in the details below.

1. Place (Area) Development

In general, the subjects rated at 3.51 or high level with the details on the safety of the community and the people's properties followed by the policy of drug free zone.

2. People (Human Resource) Development

In general, the subjects rated at 3.32 or moderate level with the details on the arrangement of community regulations and followed by the people development leading to community identity.

3. Product (Economic and Income Source) Development

In general, the subjects rated at 2.81 or moderate level with the details on the increase of community's product quality based on community identity followed by the direction of career income development.

4. Plan (Community Plan) Development

In general, the subjects rated at 2.77 or moderate level with the details on the plan for nourishing the natural resources and the environment followed by creating knowledge community and the ability of community management.

B. Results of the Focus Group

The management team mentioned some factors affecting the success factors:

1. There should be cooperation between people in the community and the community leaders especially in providing development plan. The community leaders should possess a public mind without corruption.
2. The community leaders should be the leaders in leading their lives through Sufficient Economy Philosophy and be energetic developers with knowledge seeking.
3. There should be a meeting seeking for local wisdom from the past to present including experiences to develop local products with clear community identity.
4. Support and encourage academic training for people in the community to develop the potential of the people and to increase the family's income.

Guidelines for developing community management process

1. People (Human Resource) Development

There should be an encouragement to make people pay attention on their community. People in the community should be honest and sacrifice for the benefit of the community.

2. Place (Area) Development

There should be prioritization to develop the community and direct the community's future.

3. Product (Economic and Income Source) Development

There should be a development on additional occupations to increase income of the family and the community leading to strong and sustainable community.

4. Plan (Community Plan) Development

There should be a regular meeting of the community leaders to set the community plan and resolve the community problems.

V. DISCUSSION

On the area development, there should be a policy to promote the safety in the community by using voluntary system. On the economic and income source aspect, there should be a measure on value added of the community's products focusing on the community identity. The Government sector should give the knowledge to the people in the community to apply local wisdom with the modern technology to increase better quality of the agricultural and local community products [4]. Giving values on Thai local

wisdom and strengthening career development based on sustainability of natural resources and environment [5]. Preserve the natural resources of the community, there should be the reduction or the quit of chemicals in production and making the most of natural resources. Factor affecting the success of the community leaders in people development is the activity promoting cooperation and unity in the community. The key points of the social dimension and ethics and virtues include the relationship and generosity in the community, community reliance, unity, and sharing. These characteristics identify the integrity of unity, sufficiency, and sacrifice which encouraging the community's potential development and increase self virtues whilst being social capital resulting in community self reliance and community strength.

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